

Tumor cells may change dream images by inducing a delay in transformation of spinor states between the heart and the brain

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Abstract: Spinors within the structures of the heart, brain, blood cells and neurons form an entangled system which exchange information through photons and spinor waves. Photons have the limited velocity, while spinor waves have the infinite velocity and transmit information immediately. This difference between the velocities of transferring information by these waves causes to the oscillations of the heart and brain cells and emergence of classical and quantum electrical and magnetic fields. Quantum fields and states of spinors and photons are corresponded to information bits which they store. On the other hand, magnetic and electrical fields cause to the acceleration of spinors and photons and emergence of the Rindler space-time. In this space-time, there are two regions which time, position and the arrow of spinors in each region is different respect to ones in other region. This gives this possibility that spinors could store information bits of different times and positions. During sleeping, these information bits may form points of dream images. For example, when one sees a point in time $t=t_0$ and position $x=x_0$ when he is wake, its information could be stored in two spinor states in time $t=t_1$ and position $x=x_1$ in region I and time $t=t_2$ and position $x=x_2$ in regions II. During dream, these points are joined and a line could be seen. These spinors may form triplet states with other spinors which each state of it could be related to one of main colors: Red, Blue and Green. Thus, a dark or white point may be converted to a colorful line during dream. If a tumor is emerged, according to the Warburg proposal, products and number of spinors radiated by cells are changed. Consequently, during dream, some differences in time, position and number of points are emerged and a colorful line may be converted to a looped shape with different colors. Thus, tumors have a direct effect on dream images.

Keywords: Dream; Spinor; Photon; Heart; Brain; Tumor

I. Introduction

Up to date, it has been known that different diseases like tumors have direct effects on sleeping. This is because that tumors change the biological properties of cells and have direct effects on the process of exchanging information between neurons. For example, some authors have considered the tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF) biology and its role in sleep, and describe how TNF medications influence sleep/wake activity [1]. Another authors have shown that tumors promote IL-6 driven inflammation and changes in metabolism and sleep. This could be associated with aberrant activity of hypocretin/orexin (HO) neurons. They have stated that blocking HO signaling attenuated metabolic abnormalities and enhanced sleep quality [2]. Another paper has argued that patients with pediatric brain tumor demonstrate several aspects of abnormal sleep, which are associated with poorer long-term patient-reported outcomes [3]. Another article has discussed that sleep problems occur among half of childhood brain

tumor survivors with neurocognitive problems, and are associated with worse executive functioning [4]. Another study has indicated that primary brain tumor (PBT) patients report sleep disturbance due to their disease and treatment [5]. Another findings have presented information regarding the epidemiological and biological aspects of prostate cancer, and discussed the impact of sleep physiology and sleep disorders on this type of cancer, highlighting possible associations with risk of cancer development [6]. Another group have determined the effect of transsphenoidal surgery on quality of life and sleep in patients with pituitary adenomas and shown that it depends on tumor type and compression of the optic chiasm [7]. Another researchers have determined the prevalence and predictors of sleep disturbance in people with malignant brain tumors and caregivers, and explored any relationship between the patient-caregiver dyad's sleep [8].

Now, the question arises that what is the relation between tumors and dreams? A dream is a collection of images that usually occur involuntarily in the mind during certain stages of sleep. Humans spend about two hours dreaming per night, and each dream lasts around 5 to 20 minutes [9-12]. These images may be produced by evolutions of biological molecules and cells and it is natural that there be a relation between tumors and dream. For example, according to the Warburg proposal [13,14], metabolism and products of tumor cells are different respect to normal cells. These products change many biological process and have the main effects on dream images.

In this research, we propose a model which considers the relation between number of radiated spinors from tumor cells and dream images. In this model, first, we describe how entangled spinors within a biological body store information and also how these stored informations are appeared as dream images. Then, we will show that tumor cells change the entangled system of spinors and have direct effects on dream.

The Outline of papers is as follows: In section II, we describe the model and disclose the spinor techniques in producing dream images. In section III, we formulate the model. The last section is devoted to conclusion.

II. The model: Emergence of dream images from combining information bits stored in different times and positions:

During dream, when an image is appeared, each point of it may be related to information bits which stored within neurons and cells in one special time. These information bits are stored by spinor states. For example, each state of the arrows of spinors and their motions may be related to an information bit. The velocity of transferring information between spinors is more than the velocity of light. It means that any information bit could be transferred between two separated points immediately. While, photons move with the limited velocity (for example, the velocity of light). This difference between needed time for transferring information by spinor and photon

waves between two pints could cause to oscillations of spinors. These oscillations themselves could produce new states which provide new possibilities for storing information. To produce these oscillations, suppose, two anti-parallel spinors are placed on a circle or a loop(See Figure 1):

A: Two anti-parallel spins exchange photons which force on them to move towards each other. Reversely, some virtual spinors are emerged with opposite spins which move in reverse direction and cause to a change in the arrow of initial spinors.

B: After reversing spinors, initial exchanged photons have the memory of previous stage and by reach the spinors, repel them.

C: By passing time, new photons are produced which have new information and attract spinors.

These types of loops could be seen in both neural and blood circularly systems. For example (See Figure 2):

A: First, Spinors and charges on the heart produce both types of classical and quantum magnetic and electrical fields:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{classic,Heart} &= E_{Qu1,Heart} + E_{Qu2,Heart} + \dots + E_{Qu n,Heart} \\
 B_{classic,Heart} &= B_{Qu1,Heart} + B_{Qu2,Heart} + \dots + B_{Qu n,Heart}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

Where $E_{classic,Heart}/B_{classic,Heart}$ are the classic electrical and magnetic fields and $E_{Qu1,Heart}/B_{Qu1,Heart}$ are the quantum electrical and magnetical fields. Classical fields could be observed and detected by present detectors; while quantum fields couldn't be detected normally and only spinors could take them.

B: Spinors on the heart give their information to iron atoms and spinors on hemoglobin and other blood molecules. These spinors move along the vessels and give information to spinors and ions within the neurons. These spinors move and produce below classical and magnetic fields between neurons:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{classic,Brain} &= E_{Qu1,Brain} + E_{Qu2,Brain} + \dots + E_{Qu n,Brain} \\
 B_{classic,Brain} &= B_{Qu1,Brain} + B_{Qu2,Brain} + \dots + B_{Qu n,Brain}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2}$$

C: Spinors within the neurons move and give their informations to spinors on blood cells. These cells return to the heart and produce the oscillation motions.

Now, the question arises that what is the relation between dream images and these processes of exchanging information bits? To response this question, suppose that (See Figure 3):

1. In time $t=t_1$, one sees a point. The existence of this point could be related to the existence of a spinor. The non-existence of this point could be related to non-existence of a spinor within neural and blood system.
2. For an existence state of a point and a spinor, the acceleration of particles between neurons or within blood vessels and also biological loops cause to the emergence of some Unruh temperatures and a Rindler space-time. In this space-time, there are two regions which observers see a point, a spinor and a type of time in each region. Spins of spinors in two regions are in opposite respect to each other. Thus, initial point in time $t=t_0$ converts to two points in two times $t=t_1$ and $t=t_2$ in two regions of the Rindler Space-time. Maybe, one time relates to the past and one relates to future.
3. Colors of a point could be represented by three states of a triplet of spinors in each region of this Rindler Space-time. For example : $\uparrow\uparrow \rightarrow$ Red , $\downarrow\downarrow \rightarrow$ Blue, $(\uparrow\uparrow + \downarrow\downarrow) \rightarrow$ Green
4. Colors of a point in one region may be the reverse the colors of a point in other region. Because, the arrows of spinors are reverse to each other.
5. When a dream images is emerged, observer sees a colorful line instead of initial point.

Above dream image is corresponded to a normal health person. However, a patient sees different dream images. This is because that any disease change the spinor states within the vessels and neurons. For example, according to the Warburg proposal, products and number of radiated spinors from normal and tumor cells are different. Thus, when a tumor is emerged, number and states of spinors change and consequently, a delay in transformation information from a heart to a brain occurs. This delay causes that non-existence and existence states change person sees more than two points or nothing instead of initial point which was stored in his memory. Or maybe, instead of a line, a person sees a curved during dream (See Figure 4).

Fig 1: Differences between velocities of photons and spinor waves cause to the oscillations of entangled spinors.

Figure 2: An entangled system from spinors on blood molecules and neurons

Figure 3: The process of formation of dream by spinor states

Figure 4: Effect of tumor cells on spinor states and dream images

III. Mathematical Results:

Each information bit could be stored by a spinor state. These states are emerged by evolutions of spinors in a curved space-time. This space-time is produced by Unruh temperature [15,16].

$$T_{Unruh,\uparrow} = \frac{a_{spinor,\uparrow}}{2\pi} \quad (3)$$

Where $T_{Unruh,\uparrow}$ is the Unruh temperature and $a_{spinor,\uparrow}$ is the acceleration of spinor. This total spinor acceleration could be divided into several different accelerations which are produced by different forces and motions:

$$a_{spinor,\uparrow} = a_{spinor,\uparrow,1} + a_{spinor,\uparrow,2} + a_{spinor,\uparrow,3} + a_{spinor,\uparrow,4} + \dots \quad (4)$$

For example, motions of a spinor with the velocity ($V_{Spinor,\uparrow}$) around a curved line with radius ($r_{bio-circle}$) produces the below acceleration:

$$a_{spinor,\uparrow,1} = \frac{V_{Spinor,\uparrow}^2}{r_{bio-circle}} \quad (5)$$

On the other hand, motions of spinors with charges (Q) and the velocity ($V_{Spinor,\uparrow}$) lead to below current:

$$i_{Spinor,\uparrow} = QV_{Spinor,\uparrow} \quad (6)$$

This current produces the below magnetic field:

$$B_{spinor,\uparrow,2} = \frac{\mu_0 i_{Spinor,\uparrow}}{2\pi r_{bio-circle}} = \frac{\mu_0 Q_{Spinor,\uparrow} V_{Spinor,\uparrow}}{2\pi r_{bio-circle}} \quad (7)$$

This magnetic field forces on spinors and produces the below acceleration:

$$a_{spinor,\uparrow,2} = \frac{F_{spinor,\uparrow,2}}{m_e} = \frac{QV_{Spinor,\uparrow} B_{spinor,\uparrow,2}}{m_e} = \frac{\mu_0 Q^2_{Spinor,\uparrow} V_{Spinor,\uparrow}^2}{2\pi m_e r_{bio-circle}} \quad (8)$$

Where $F_{Spinor,\uparrow,2}$ is the magnetic force and m_e is the spinor mass. Also, the spin of spinors themselves produce forces, magnetic fields and acceleration:

$$a_{spinor,\uparrow,3} = \frac{F_{spinor,\uparrow,3}}{m_e} = \frac{QV_{Spinor,\uparrow} S_{spinor,\uparrow,3}}{m_e} \quad (9)$$

The magnetic field of spinors have direct relations with spins:

$$B_{spinor,\uparrow,4} \approx \epsilon S_{spinor,\uparrow,4} \quad (10)$$

This magnetic field produces the below magnetic energy density ($U_{spinor,\uparrow,4}$):

$$U_{spinor,\uparrow,4} = \frac{(B_{spinor,\uparrow,4})^2}{2\mu_0} = \frac{(S_{spinor,\uparrow,4})^2}{2\mu_0}$$

(11)

This density ($U_{spinor,\uparrow,4}$): could produce the below energy within a volume with the radius of ($r_{bio-circle}$):

$$E_{spinor,\uparrow,4} = \frac{4\pi}{3} U_{spinor,\uparrow,4} (r_{bio-circle})^3 \quad (12)$$

Taking derivative of above energy respect to the radius ($r_{bio-circle}$) gives the below force ($F_{spinor,\uparrow,4}$):

$$F_{spinor,\uparrow,4} = -\frac{dE_{spinor,\uparrow,4}}{d r_{bio-circle}} = -4\pi U_{spinor,\uparrow,4} (r_{bio-circle})^2 \quad (13)$$

This force produces the below acceleration:

$$a_{spinor,\uparrow,4} = \frac{F_{spinor,\uparrow,4}}{m_e} = -\frac{4\pi U_{spinor,\uparrow,4} (r_{bio-circle})^2}{m_e} \quad (14)$$

Above accelerations could be summed and produce a total acceleration.

This acceleration produces a curved space-time. In this space-time, two regions are emerged. Each region has itself properties. For example, the observer in region I sees different time respect to the observer in region II. Existence or non-existence of information bits in two regions are completely entangled. For example, non-existence of a point could be defined by below states:

$$|0nonexistence, E_{Spinor,\uparrow}\rangle_{I,Past,t=t1} |0nonexistence, E_{Spinor,\downarrow}\rangle_{II,Future,t=t2} \quad (15)$$

Where $|0nonexistence, E_{Spinor,\uparrow}\rangle_{I,Past,t=t1}$ is the non-existence state of a point in time t=t1 and $|0nonexistence, E_{Spinor,\downarrow}\rangle_{II,Future,t=t2}$ is the non-existence state of a point in time t=t2. Also, existence of a point could be presented by below states:

$$|1existence, \uparrow, E_{Spinor,\uparrow}\rangle_{I,Past,t=t1} |1existence, \downarrow, E_{Spinor,\downarrow}\rangle_{II,Future,t=t2} \quad (16)$$

Where $|1existence, \uparrow, E_{Spinor,\uparrow}\rangle_{I,Past,t=t1}$ is the existence state of a point in time t=t1 and $|1existence, \downarrow, E_{Spinor,\downarrow}\rangle_{II,Future,t=t2}$ is the existence state of a point in time t=t2. Total state of

a point including existence and non-existence states in two regions and two different times could be obtained from below equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
|Point State, \uparrow\rangle &= |1 Bit Information, \uparrow\rangle \\
&= \cos(\alpha_{T_{Unruh, spinor, \uparrow}}) |0nonexistence, E_{Spinor, \uparrow}\rangle_{I, Past, t=t1} |0nonexistence, E_{Spinor, \downarrow}\rangle_{II, Future, t=t2} \\
&+ \sin(\alpha_{T_{Unruh, spinor, \uparrow}}) |1existence, \uparrow, E_{Spinor, \uparrow}\rangle_{I, Past, t=t1} |1existence, \downarrow, E_{Spinor, \downarrow}\rangle_{II, Future, t=t2}
\end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

Where $\cos^2(\alpha_{T_{Unruh, spinor, \uparrow}})$ and $\sin^2(\alpha_{T_{Unruh, spinor, \uparrow}})$ are the probability for the non-existence ($P_{nonexistence, \uparrow}$) and existence ($P_{existence, \uparrow}$) of a point in two different times and have the below relation with the energy of spinors ($E_{Spinor, \uparrow}$) and the Unruh temperature ($T_{Unruh, \uparrow}$):

$$\tanh \alpha_{T_{Unruh, spinor, \uparrow}} = \exp\left(-\frac{E_{Spinor, \uparrow}}{T_{Unruh, \uparrow}}\right) \tag{18}$$

We can define probabilities as:

$$\begin{aligned}
P_{nonexistence, \uparrow} &= \cos^2(\alpha_{T_{Unruh, spinor, \uparrow}}) \\
P_{existence, \uparrow} &= \sin^2(\alpha_{T_{Unruh, spinor, \uparrow}})
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

And write the below relation between probabilities:

$$P_{nonexistence, \uparrow} + P_{existence, \uparrow} = 1 \tag{20}$$

To produce line states, we need to four points in two times t=t1 and t=t2 and two places x=x1 and x=x2. Thus, we can define 2 bit information state which is obtained from combing two 1 bit information states with opposite spins in two times and two different places:

$$\begin{aligned}
|Line State, \uparrow\downarrow\rangle &= |2 Bit Information, \uparrow\downarrow\rangle = \\
&\cos(\Theta_{\uparrow\downarrow}) |1 Bit Information, \uparrow\rangle_{x=x1} |1 Bit Information, \downarrow\rangle_{x=x2} \\
&+ \sin(\Theta_{\uparrow\downarrow}) |1 Bit Information, \downarrow\rangle_{x=x1} |1 Bit Information, \uparrow\rangle_{x=x2}
\end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

Above line state shows the probability for producing two lines from four spinors. We can define below probabilities:

$$P_{line,\uparrow\downarrow} = \cos^2(\Theta_{\uparrow\downarrow})$$

$$P_{line\downarrow\uparrow} = \sin^2(\Theta_{\uparrow\downarrow})$$

(22)

And write the below relation between probabilities:

$$P_{line,\uparrow\downarrow} + P_{line\downarrow\uparrow} = 1$$

(23)

Above line could be colorful. Each color from main colors (Red, Blue, Green) could be defined by a state of three triplet states:

$$|\uparrow, \uparrow\rangle \rightarrow \text{Red}$$

$$|\downarrow, \downarrow\rangle \rightarrow \text{Blue}$$

$$\{|\uparrow, \uparrow\rangle + |\downarrow, \downarrow\rangle\} \rightarrow \text{Green}$$

(24)

Thus, two color full line states in two times $t=t_1$ and $t=t_2$ and two points $x=x_1$ and $x=x_2$ could be defined by:

$$|\text{Color Line State}\rangle = |\text{12 Bit Information}\rangle =$$

$$P_{Red}|\text{2 Bit Information, } \uparrow\downarrow\rangle \otimes |\text{2 Bit Information, } \uparrow\downarrow\rangle$$

$$P_{Blue}|\text{2 Bit Information, } \downarrow\uparrow\rangle \otimes |\text{2 Bit Information, } \downarrow\uparrow\rangle$$

$$P_{Green}\{|\text{2 Bit Information, } \downarrow\uparrow\rangle \otimes |\text{2 Bit Information, } \downarrow\uparrow\rangle$$

$$+ |\text{2 Bit Information, } \downarrow\uparrow\rangle \otimes |\text{2 Bit Information, } \downarrow\uparrow\rangle\}$$

(25)

Where

$$P_{Red} + P_{Blue} + P_{Green} = 1$$

(26)

And

$P_{Red}/P_{Blue}/P_{Green}$ are probabilities related to colors of lines. Between two points along a colorful line, photons move which their states could be defined as:

$$|photon, state\rangle = \frac{1}{\cosh r_{T_{Unruh,photon}}} \sum_m^M \tanh^m r_{T_{Unruh,photon}} |m\uparrow\uparrow, I\rangle |m\downarrow\downarrow, II\rangle \quad (27)$$

where

$$\tanh r_{T_{Unruh,photon}} = \exp\left(-\frac{E_{photon}}{T_{Unruh,photon}}\right)$$

$$T_{Unruh,photon} = \frac{V_{photon}^2}{2\pi r} + \frac{a_{spinor,\uparrow}}{2\pi} + \frac{a_{spinor,\downarrow}}{2\pi} \quad (28)$$

And $T_{Unruh,photon}$ is the Unruh temperature for photons and V_{photon} is the velocity of photons.

By exchanging photons, colors of points and their spins change. Thus, total state of two colorful lines could be obtained from below equation:

$$\begin{aligned} |Evaluated - Color Line State\rangle &= |n \text{ Bit Information}\rangle = \\ &\{P_{Red}|2 \text{ Bit Information}, \uparrow\downarrow\rangle \otimes |2 \text{ Bit Information}, \uparrow\downarrow\rangle \\ &P_{Blue}|2 \text{ Bit Information}, \downarrow\uparrow\rangle \otimes |2 \text{ Bit Information}, \downarrow\uparrow\rangle \\ &P_{Green}\{|2 \text{ Bit Information}, \downarrow\uparrow\rangle \otimes |2 \text{ Bit Information}, \downarrow\uparrow\rangle\} \otimes |photon, state\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

However, above equation describe the exchanged information between two points on a cell. Within a biological system, information could be transmitted between cells. In these conditions, exchanged photon states between two pints l and k could be obtained from below equation:

$$|photon, transmitted, ij\rangle =$$

$$\frac{1}{\cosh r_{T_{Unruh,photon,i}}} \sum_l^L \tanh^l r_{T_{Unruh,photon,i}} |l, i\uparrow\uparrow, I\rangle |l, i\downarrow\downarrow, II\rangle \otimes$$

$$\frac{1}{\cosh r_{T_{Unruh,photon,j}}} \sum_k^K \tanh^k r_{T_{Unruh,photon,j}} |k, j\downarrow\downarrow, I\rangle |k, j\uparrow\uparrow, II\rangle$$

(30)

Thus, total states of two colorful lines could be transmitted between two points by below wave function:

$$|Transmitted Evaluated - Color Line State between two pints, ij\rangle$$

$$= |n \text{ Bit Information between two pints, } ij\rangle =$$

$$= \sum_{ij} \widetilde{P}_{ij} |n \text{ Bit Information between two pints, } i\rangle \otimes$$

$$|n \text{ Bit Information between two pints, } j\rangle \otimes$$

$$|photon, transmitted, ij\rangle$$

(31)

Where $|n \text{ Bit Information between two pints, } i\rangle$ is the information of two colorful lines in point or cell i, $|n \text{ Bit Information between two pints, } j\rangle$ is the information of two colorful lines in point or cell j and $|photon, transmitted, ij\rangle$ is the state of photon which moves between points i and j.

Photonic energy which is transmitted between two points i and j has the below relation with the frequency ($\nu_{Photon,ij}$) and the wavelength ($\lambda_{Photon,ij}$)

$$E_{Photon,ij} = h\nu_{Photon,ij} = \frac{h c}{\lambda_{Photon,ij}} \rightarrow \lambda_{Photon,ij} = \frac{h c}{E_{Photon,ij}}$$

(32)

Thus, time period for this photon is:

$$t_{periodPhoton,ij} = \frac{h}{E_{Photon,ij}} \quad (33)$$

On the other hand, number of photons (n_{ij}) with the wavelength ($\lambda_{Photon,ij}$) which are exchanging between two points by a separation distance ($l_{Photon,ij}$) could be obtained from below equation:

$$\rightarrow n_{ij} = \frac{l_{Photon,ij}}{\lambda_{Photon,ij}} \quad (34)$$

Thus, total time which lasts a photon goes from point i to j could be obtained by below relation:

$$t_{exchanged\ photon,ij} = n_{ij} t_{periodPhoton,ij} = n_{ij} \frac{h}{E_{Photon,ij}} \quad (35)$$

Where h is the plank constant. On the other hand, near a heavy cell, a photon with spin 1 could decay into two spinors with spin 1/2:

$$Photon \rightarrow 2\ spinor \rightarrow E_{Photon,ij} \rightarrow 2\ E_{Spinor,\uparrow} \quad (36)$$

Thus, exchanged photons could produce exchanged electrons which their needed time for passing the separation distance between points i and j could be obtained from below equation:

$$t_{exchanged\ electron,ij} = n_{ij} \frac{h}{E_{Spinor,\uparrow}} = n_{ij} \frac{2h}{E_{Photon,ij}} \quad (37)$$

To obtain the needed time for transformation of information within a bio-system, we should first, define the number operator:

$$\mathcal{N}_{ij} = \sum_{ij} \widetilde{P}_{ij} [\widetilde{g}_i g_j + \widetilde{e}_i e_j] \quad (38)$$

Where \widetilde{e}_i, e_j are creation/annihilation operators for spinors and have the below definitions:

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{e}_i |0\rangle &= |1\rangle \\ e_j |1\rangle &= |0\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

And \widetilde{g}_i, g_j are creation/annihilation operators for photons and have the below definitions:

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{g}_i |0\rangle &= |1\rangle \\ g_j |1\rangle &= |0\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

Using these operators, we can obtain total quantum time which information of two colorful line states need to pass a separation distance in a biological system:

$$\begin{aligned} t_{tot} &= \sum_{ij} \widetilde{P}_{ij} \langle n \text{ Bit Information between two pints, } ij | \otimes \\ &\mathcal{N}_{ij} [t_{\text{exchanged electron, } ij} + t_{\text{exchanged photon, } ij}] \otimes \\ &|n \text{ Bit Information between two pints, } ij \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

During sleeping, all informations which store in different times and places are gathered and some shapes like two colorful lines are emerged. The needed time for producing these lines can be obtained from above equations. Now, the question arises that what is the effect of tumors on the sleep imaging. According to the Warburg proposal, number of spinors and other products of normal and tumor cells are different. Thus, the number operator and also states and Unruh temperatures changes and needed time for the emergence of each point of image will be differ. For example, in these conditions, the needed time for the emergence of two colorful lines could be obtained from below equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
t''_{tot,tumor+normal} &= \sum_{ij} \widehat{P}_{ij} \langle n \text{ Bit Information between two pints, } ij | \otimes \\
&N_{ij} [t_{exchanged\ electron,ij} + t_{exchanged\ photon,ij}] \otimes \\
&|n \text{ Bit Information between two pints, } ij \rangle + \\
&\sum_{ij} \overline{P}_{ij,tumor} \langle n \text{ Bit Information between two pints related to tumor, } ij | \otimes \\
&\Delta_{ij} [t''_{tumor,exchanged\ electron,ij} + t''_{tumor,exchanged\ photon,ij}] \otimes \\
&|n \text{ Bit Information between two pints related to tumor, } ij \rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{42}$$

This difference in time of emergence of points and lines in an image for normal person and patient cause that shapes within their dreams be different. Thus, by considering dreams, we can understand any problem which occurs within a body.

Conclusions:

In this research, we have proposed a mathematical model which allows to consider the effect of tumor cells on dream images. In this model, spinors around or within the heart cells give information to spinors on the hemoglobin molecules and blood cells. These spinors move along vessels, interact with spinors and ions within the neurons and give their informations to them. Motions of these spinors produce quantum and classic electrical and magnetic fields. These fields cause to the accelerations of photons and electrons and create a Rindler Space-time. This space-time has two regions which spinor and photon states in each region are different respect to ones in other region. Also, time and positions of spinors in two regions are different. For example, a spinor may store information of the past and other spinor may store information of future. Each information could be divided into many bits which stores in spinor and spin states of two regions. When, one sleeps, information bits of different times and positions are gathered and form points of an image. For example, if one sees a dark point by his eyes when he is wake, during sleeping, this point converts to two points which are joined and form a line. If spinors which store informations of these points form some triplet states with other spinors, each state of this triplet could be related to a main Red, Blue and Green color. Consequently, the initial point converts to a colorful line within a dream. However, when a tumor is emerged, spinor structures of system destroy and some new spinors are emerged. These spinors make a delay in transferring information between cells and change the shape of dream images. Thus, by considering dream images, we can diagnose some types of tumors.

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